

IDENTIFICATION OF CLUSTERS IN PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF WATER SAMPLES FROM AN IMPORTANT LOCAL RIVER

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Abstract

This article focuses on the analysis of data obtained from water samples taken from the Reconquista River, one of the most significant rivers in Buenos Aires, Argentina. The aim of this study is to identify clusters within the data that may reveal patterns of contamination or variations in water quality. It explains the methods used for data treatment and the application of a specific machine learning algorithm to analyze the dataset. The results are presented along with the hypotheses generated from these findings. Finally, it discusses the implications of the results and proposes areas for future research to further understand and improve the water quality of the Reconquista River.

Keywords: *Water, Physico-chemistry, Artificial Intelligence, Clustering.*

1 Introduction

The Reconquista River basin covers a total of 82 km, from its source at the confluence of the streams La Choza and El Durazno, to its mouth at the Luján River. In figure 1 we can visualise its scope.

Figure 1. Map provided by COMIREC showing the boundaries of the Reconquista river basin.

There are many industries whose waste is discharged into the river. Today it is the second most polluted basin

in Buenos Aires (surpassed only by the Matanza-Riachuelo basin) (Nader, G.M., 2015) (Castilla V., Canevaro, S., López, B., 2021). Figure 2 shows an image that attempts to summarise the state of the Reconquista River.

Figure 2. Tortoises lying on rubbish bags and among other waste.

In order to understand the dimensions of the problem in question, it is important to consider that, according to the Argentine census of 2022, there is a total population of more than 1,000,000 people living between Merlo and Moreno (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2023). These people are directly or indirectly exposed to unhealthy conditions on a daily basis.

2 Objectives

To analyse the behaviour and current situation of a section of the upper basin of the Reconquista River, as well as the streams that flow into it, using statistical and artificial intelligence tools to search for patterns or relationships between the data of physico-chemical variables of water samples.

3 Methodologies

Since May 2023, the same research team has been collecting water samples, analysing a total of 10 physico-chemical parameters from each of them using validated

methods, obtaining a total of 220 rows of data to date. This work has been published under the title “Análisis del Río de la Reconquista” published in the scientific journal *Ingeniería Sanitaria y Ambiental* (Ferrán, N.E., Pastorini, M.E., López, C.G., Fernández, E., Esperanza, M.F., 2023).

This article focuses on the use of unsupervised machine learning techniques to extract relevant information from the analysis of this dataset.

Unsupervised learning allows us to discover hidden structures in the data. Unlike supervised learning, in this case we do not work with labelled data to train the models, as the goal is not to predict the output class (Mohammed J. Zaki, Wagner Meira, Jr., 2020). Thus, in the absence of labelled data, we can only discover patterns that occur naturally in the dataset. One of the main techniques of unsupervised learning is clustering. The aim of this method is to find groups of instances (called clusters) that are related to each other. This technique has countless applications, such as anomaly detection, customer segmentation or recommender systems. There are several types of clustering algorithms, each of which identifies clusters in a different way. In this article, the popular *k-means* algorithm is used. Its steps are as follows:

1. Initialisation: k initial centroids are chosen from the data, either by selecting them randomly or using specific techniques to choose them.
2. Assignment of values to centroids: each value is associated with the nearest centroid, which implies grouping it with the option whose distance (usually Euclidean) is the minimum.
3. Centroid update: after the data has been distributed among the different clusters, the centroids are adjusted by recalculating the mean of all the data in each group. This positions the centroids at new locations based on the clustered data.
4. Iteration: Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until the distribution of the data no longer changes significantly or a limit of iterations is reached.

The goal of *k-means* is to minimise intra-cluster variability and maximise inter-cluster variability to achieve meaningful clustering of the data. However, it can be sensitive to the choice of initial centroids and can sometimes get trapped in local optima (Ian H. Witten, Eibe Frank, Mark A. Hall, Christopher J. Pal, 2016).

Scaling is a crucial step prior to the application of the *k-means* algorithm (Raschka S., 2014). This technique consists of normalising data features so that they have a uniform and comparable scale. When applying *K-means* to unscaled data, features with wider ranges may dominate the clustering process, which could lead to biased or

inaccurate results. Scaling the data ensures that all features have equal weight in the analysis, allowing the algorithm to identify patterns and intrinsic structures more accurately. This improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the algorithm, contributing to more representative clusters.

In this case, the scaling technique used was *z-score*. Its implementation consist of equation 1:

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where

- z : normalised value (z-score)
- x : non-normalised value
- μ : mean value
- σ : standard deviation

Regarding *k-means* algorithm implementation, the following parameters were chosen:

- k value equal to 3.
- Initialisation method *k-means++*, an intelligent method of selecting initial centroids (Vassilvitskii, S., Arthur, D., 2007).

4 Results and Discussion

After running the algorithm, the result is shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3. Results of the clustering algorithm applied to the DO vs. pH scatter plot.

Three different clusters can be visualised. Below is a discussion of each:

- The red one contains points in a lower pH range than the rest and in a lower Dissolved Oxygen (DO) range. Therefore it has been decided to call it "acidic samples with low O_2 level".

- The green one contains points in a higher pH range than the rest and in a higher DO range. It was decided to call it "Alkaline samples with good O_2 level".
- The yellow one is considered as an intermediate between the two previous ones. It contains points in an intermediate pH range and the same for the DO range. It has been decided to call it "Neutral samples with poor O_2 level".

The literature indicates that the minimum DO concentration for aquatic life to thrive in a water body is 4 parts per million, while values lower than this indicate a serious problem (Chang J., Pulla E., 2007). Note that most of the points in the green cluster have DO concentrations above this number.

The same scatterplot was then analysed by distinguishing the values by sampling point (figure 4) and by month of sampling (figure 5).

Figure 4. Scatter plot of DO vs. pH with values segregated by sampling point.

Figure 5. Scatter plot of DO vs. pH with values segregated by month of sampling.

In figure 4 a density of light blue points can be observed in the upper right corner of the graph, i.e. in high ranges of both pH and DO. These points belong to the Las Torres stream, which could be related to some kind of upstream treatment. On the other hand, there is a density of red points in low DO ranges, belonging to the Falbo

Bridge. The latter could be related to the effect of different wastes that could be dumped upstream.

As for figure 5, a density of brown and pink dots can be observed in a low range of DO, corresponding to the months of October and November respectively. These are the hottest months sampled. On the other hand, there is a density of orange dots in a high range of DO and pH, corresponding to June, one of the coldest months in which samples were taken. This last analysis could indicate a correlation between water quality and season.

5 Conclusions

Although the project is still at an early stage and the amount of data is still small, the results presented show that it is possible to generate hypotheses and draw certain conclusions about the behaviour and current situation of the Reconquista River and the streams that flow into it, thus fulfilling the objective initially proposed. These hypotheses and conclusions will gain statistical robustness with more data, either by increasing the number of parameters measured and/or by increasing the sampling frequency. It is hoped that both of these issues will be addressed by the research team in the future.

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